

THE CURRENT STATE OF THE METHODOLOGY FOR DEVELOPING INFORMATION COMPETENCE OF THE FUTURE PRIMARY CLASS TEACHERS UNDER DIGITAL CONDITIONS

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***Abstract.** All higher education institutions in Uzbekistan need to improve the methodology of teaching information technology to future elementary school teachers in the new Digitization conditions. In this regard, the importance of students in education, their professional functions in the labor market as a whole, and this, in turn, led to an increase in the tendency to develop and the development of professional communicative competences by means of information and communication technologies.*

***Keywords:** technologies, information, professional communicative, programs, traditional tasks.*

All higher education institutions in Uzbekistan need to improve the methodology of teaching information technology to future elementary school teachers in the new Digitization conditions. In this regard, the importance of students in education, their professional functions in the labor market as a whole, and this, in turn, led to an increase in the tendency to develop and the development of professional communicative competences by means of information and communication technologies. The education policy of each higher education institution should be aimed at solving the problem of training of competitive specialists who are socially protected, adapted to constantly changing conditions and have developed professional communicative competence.

In the initial stages of development, programs for the use of information and communication technologies in the educational process were developed, ideas about their use in the educational process were positively and critically re-examined, and methodological bases for their use in the educational process were created. In the course of the lesson, suggestions that it is possible to organize full education only from information and communication technologies without the teacher interfering with the lesson were rejected. However, information and communication technologies have not only freed teachers from the usual, traditional tasks, but also imposed tasks related to programming, teaching materials and technical coordination.

In order for information and communication technologies to be a powerful factor in the effectiveness of the didactic process, they should correspond to the goal-content program of this process and help to implement the main functions of pedagogical management.

Therefore, in order to improve the methodology of teaching information technology to future primary school teachers in the context of Digitization in the educational process, the teacher must know the right balance between technology tools, teaching methods and approaches. . The most important thing is that the use of information and communication technologies in education develops the professional communicative competence of students, the

opportunity to develop research skills, intellectual competence to develop independence, creative thinking, cognitive activity, reasoning, writing essays and checking skills.

In the conditions of digitization, the future primary class teachers were distinguished by the rapid development of research in areas where it is possible to improve the methodology of teaching information technology. Later, one of several Uzbek scientists, R. J. Ishmuhamedov, suggested that it is better to use information and communication technologies in primary classes, to perform the tasks of consultants, partners and for educational purposes.

Thus, in the conditions of digitalization, it is necessary to improve the methodology of teaching information technology to future elementary school teachers, to develop programs to support the use of information and communication technologies for teaching in elementary school, and to develop training and test programs. output, development of computer courses, distance learning, we can see that the use of the Internet in classrooms is effective.

1-Table

Availability of appropriate pedagogical software

Various software tools are used in teaching. There are ready-to-use programs that do not require intervention (they are created in cooperation with programmers and teachers who develop methodological materials). Other programs give the teacher some freedom in choosing features, tasks, examples, etc. A separate group is organized by shell programs, and the teacher can independently complete the teaching material.

In the conditions of digitization, the future primary class provides new opportunities for teachers to improve the teaching methodology of information technologies. Using the Internet allows you to conduct online classes in real time. Learning on the basis of information and communication technologies in the primary school consists in developing students' professional communication skills, organizing live communication and activity in computer networks.

In the primary class, programs have been developed through teaching with the help of information and communication technologies.

In the conditions of digitalization, the improvement of the teaching methodology of information technologies for the future elementary school teachers will lead to its informatization. On the basis of information, a personal computer, tens and hundreds of gigabytes of optical disks that allow storing the contents of entire libraries in a compact form, optical fiber communication channels, video-text communication systems, methods of presenting information and knowledge, e-mail systems, etc. such fundamental discoveries lie. All technology provides the creation of a highly automated information environment, and it theoretically allows access to arbitrary knowledge at arbitrary time and in arbitrary place. Accordingly, education should provide people with the formation of new competencies necessary for them to live in the new information environment of life, including education in the conditions of wide use of modern information technologies, as well as for understanding the new integrated world and information worldview. need

Improving the teaching methodology of information technology for future elementary school teachers in the conditions of digitization (information-search, information-analytical, information-communicative, information-reflexive, information-technological, information-functional, information-professional) interactive, enhanced by synchronous and asynchronous multimedia tools (Table 2):

2-Table

Components of improving the methodology of teaching information technology to future elementary school teachers in the conditions of digitization

№	Components of information competence	Sources of information competence	Social significance	Personal importance
1.	information search	Manuals, encyclopedia, Internet	Compilation of decisions, orders, and regulatory documents	Giving new knowledge

2.	information analyst	Educational literature, mass media, Internet	Study of educational institutions	The ability to analyze any actions, situations
3.	information and communication	Telephone, mobile phones, e-mail	Advising on issues related to the provided services, preventing and resolving conflict situations	Communication with people
4.	information-reflexive	Test, questionnaires	Carrying out the necessary organizational and technical measures, conducting tests and surveys	Application of acquired or existing knowledge in life situations
5.	information technology	Telephone, mobile phones, e-mail	Working on a computer	Achieving computer literacy
6.	information-functional	Manuals, encyclopedia, Internet	Working on a computer	Achieving computer literacy
7.	information-professional	Educational literature, mass media, Internet	Professional development	Self-improvement and self-development

E.V.Dostovalova and A.M.Orbinsky suggest the use of the project method in the formation of information competence of the future teacher. O.G. Smolyaninova considers multimedia technologies as a natural environment for the formation of information competence, and emphasizes active learning methods such as controlled discovery, case method, project method and portfolio method as the most correct method of their formation.

According to M.M.Pshukova, the content of the teacher's information competence consists of knowledge, skills and competences in the field of using the following tools and methods (Fig. 1):

Figure 1. Using the following tools and methods to improve the teaching methodology of information technology for future elementary school teachers in the conditions of digitization (M.M.Pshukova)

A number of researchers point out that the structure of information competence includes two elements: single basic knowledge and skills for professionals of a voluntary profession and vocationally oriented, special knowledge and skills for a specific profession. E.V.Kasyan believes that the structure of professional information competence includes basic knowledge and skills that are common to all computer users, as well as professionally oriented knowledge and skills that ensure professional mobility and high competitiveness of a person in professional activities.

REFERENCES

1. Begimqulov U.Sh. Theory and practice of organizing and managing informatization of pedagogical educational processes.//Diss. Of the Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences. - T.: 2007.- p. 305.
2. Zaitseva O.B. Formation of information competence of future teachers by means of innovative: Diss. Paper of the Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences/ O.B.Zaitseva.- Armavir, 2002.- p. 169.
3. Zlotnikova I.Ya. Formation of information competence of a future subject teacher at a pedagogical university/I.Ya.Zlotnikova//Pedagogical info
4. Ganiyeva, M. (2023). THE MAIN DIRECTIONS OF DEVELOPING THE LOGICAL THINKING OF FUTURE ELEMENTARY SCHOOL TEACHERS (IN MATHEMATICS LESSONS). Science and innovation, 2(B3), 30-33.
5. Ganieva, M. (2023, June). EMPOWERING LOGICAL THINKING IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS THROUGH TIPS TECHNOLOGY. In Academic International Conference on Multi-Disciplinary Studies and Education (Vol. 1, No. 12, pp. 62-63).rmatics.- 2004.- No. 1.- pp. 40-44.

6. Yuldashev, U. A., Agathonov, A. A., & Butaboyev, A. A. (2023). DEVELOPMENT OF COMPETENCES IN THE FIELD OF WEB DESIGN FOR FUTURE INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY SPECIALISTS. Евразийский журнал технологий и инноваций, 1(6 Part 2), 31-37.
7. Eshbayevich, T. D., & Yuldashev, O. (2023). RAQAMLASHTIRISH SHAROITIDA TA'LIM SIFATINI OSHIRISHGA YO 'NALTIRILGAN ELEKTRON TA'LIM RESURSLARIDAN FOYDALANISH. Science and innovation, 2(Special Issue 5), 26-31.
8. Abdubanapovich, Y. U. (2023). WEB DIZAYNNI O'QITISHDA SUNNIY INTELEKTDAN FOYDALANIB BO'LAJAK INFORMATIKA O'QUVCHILARNI KOMPETENTLIGINI OSHIRISH. Science and innovation, 2(Special Issue 3), 1027-1029.
9. Abdubanapovich, Y. U. DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF PROSPECTIVE SPECIALISTS ON WEB TECHNOLOGIES. Pedagogika, 49.